

Modelling a Linear Paul Trap and Its Quantum Harmonic Behaviour: A COMSOL–MATLAB Study

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Abstract

A three-dimensional linear Paul trap was modelled using COMSOL Multiphysics to study the confinement dynamics of a singly ionized calcium ion (Ca^+) under time-dependent radio-frequency (RF) electric fields. Charged particle tracing module was used to simulate the ion trajectory inside the trap. The resulting trajectory data was exported to MATLAB, where Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis was performed to extract the secular oscillation frequency of the trapped ion. The secular frequency was observed to be approximately 500 kHz. The extracted secular frequency was then used to model the trapped ion as a quantum harmonic oscillator. Corresponding quantum wavefunctions and quantized motional energy levels were computed and visualized. The study demonstrates the connection between classical ion trapping dynamics and the quantum harmonic oscillator approximation commonly used in trapped-ion quantum systems.

1 Introduction

Paul Traps are used to trap charged ions in a periodically changing electric field. It consists of Four parallel metal blades/rods that are arranged symmetrically. A radio-frequency (RF) voltage is applied to these blades creating an oscillating potential that pushes ions toward the central axis. To prevent ions from escaping along the length of the rods, static DC voltages are applied to "end-cap" electrodes or isolated rod segments at both ends.

Figure – 1: Paul Trap

Trapped ions as a qubit are different from modern superconductor-based qubits, since they have an exceptional coherence time and high-fidelity computations but they have a slow quantum gate operation and more cost per qubit.

2 Theory

2.1 RF Trapping - The four blade electrodes create a varying electric field that oscillates at MHz Frequency range to provide

radial trapping. To provide confinement from the axis region there are end-cap electrodes that have a constant DC-Voltage applied to them so that the ion cannot escape from this axis.

The reason why trapping ions in stationary fields is impossible is because of Earnshaw Theorem, it shows that no point in a static electric field can be a stable equilibrium point, as the potential has no local minimum. So, by using alternating electric field we overcome the Earnshaw Theorem and successfully trap the ion.

2.2 Harmonic approximation – Near the centre of the Linear Paul Trap, the effective trapping potential experienced by the ion can be approximated as a parabolic potential well. In this region the electric force that is acting like a restoring force on the ion becomes proportional to its displacement from the equilibrium position, similar to the behaviour of a classical spring system.

The effective potential near the trap centre can therefore be written as:

$$U(x) \approx \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 x^2$$

Where m is the mass of the ion, ω is the secular angular frequency of oscillation and x is the displacement from the trap centre.

This approximation is valid since the ion oscillates within a small region around the equilibrium point, where higher-order nonlinear effects become negligible.

In the COMSOL simulation, the ion trajectory was obtained using charged particle tracing under time-dependent RF electric fields. The trajectory exhibited two distinct motions:

1. A fast oscillation caused by the RF driving field (micromotion),

2. A slower oscillation known as secular motion.

The secular motion represents the effective harmonic oscillation of the trapped ion. By performing a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) on the simulated trajectory data in MATLAB, secular frequency was extracted to be approximately:

$$f_{sec} \approx 500\text{KHz}$$

The corresponding angular frequency is given by:

$$\omega = 2\pi f$$

Using this angular frequency, the trapped ion system can be modelled as a quantum harmonic oscillator in the following quantum mechanical analysis.

2.3 Quantum Harmonic Oscillation - The quantum harmonic oscillator (QHO) is a fundamental model in quantum mechanics representing a particle trapped in a quadratic potential. The energy levels in a quantum harmonic oscillator are quantized and evenly spaced, it is defined by -

$$E = \hbar\omega \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

Ground state energy cannot be zero due to quantum zero-point motion. Ground state energy is -

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \hbar\omega$$

3 Simulation Methodology

3.1 COMSOL Simulation of the Linear Paul Trap - A three-dimensional linear Paul trap geometry was modelled using COMSOL Multiphysics. The simulation was performed using the Electrostatics and Charged Particle Tracing physics interfaces. The trap consisted of four blade electrodes for radial confinement and two endcap electrodes for axial confinement. Opposite blade electrode pairs were driven using time-dependent RF voltages with opposite polarity to generate a quadrupole electric field. A smaller DC voltage was applied to the endcap electrodes to provide axial trapping.

The geometric dimensions of the linear Paul trap were chosen based on the experimental trap configuration described by Guggemos *et al.* [1]

Parameters	Value
RF Voltage Amplitude	30V
RF Voltage Frequency	10 MHz
Endcap DC Voltage	5V
Ion Species	Ca ⁺
Trap Axial Length	4.5mm

Trap Radius	0.65mm
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The applied RF potentials were defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(t) &= +V_{RF} \cos(\Omega t) \\ V_2(t) &= -V_{RF} \cos(\Omega t) \end{aligned}$$

where V_{RF} is the RF amplitude and Ω is the angular driving frequency.

A singly ionized calcium ion (Ca⁺) was introduced near the centre of the trap using the Charged Particle Tracing module. The ion motion was simulated under the influence of the time-dependent electric fields generated by the electrodes.

A sufficiently refined mesh was used near the electrode surfaces to accurately resolve the electric field gradients and use less computing resources. The simulation was solved using a time-dependent study to capture both the RF micromotion and the slower secular motion of the trapped ion.

Figure – 2: Ion Trajectory

The ion trajectory data ($x(t), y(t), z(t)$) was exported from COMSOL in CSV format for further analysis in MATLAB.

3.2 MATLAB-Based Frequency and Quantum Analysis - The exported ion trajectory data from COMSOL was analysed using MATLAB. The position-time data of the trapped ion was first visualized to observe the oscillatory motion inside the trap.

Figure – 3: Ion Trajectory per axis

To determine the secular oscillation frequency, a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was performed on the ion trajectory data of x-axis. The dominant low-frequency peak in the FFT spectrum corresponded to the secular motion of the ion.

If we further more zoom into low-frequency region –

Figure – 4: FFT spectrum of ion motion along the x-axis

The low-frequency peak corresponds to the secular oscillation of the trapped ion, while the higher-frequency component near the RF driving frequency corresponds to the ion micromotion induced by the oscillating trapping field. A similar FFT-based identification of secular and micromotion frequencies has been reported in [2].

The secular frequency is extracted as approximately:

$$f_{\text{sec}} \approx 500 \text{ KHz}$$

The corresponding angular frequency was calculated using

$$\omega = 2\pi f$$

Using the extracted secular frequency a system of quantum harmonic oscillator is modelled, MATLAB is then used to compute the quantum wavefunctions and the corresponding quantized energy levels of the trapped ion. The probability density distributions for the ground and excited states are plotted

Figure – 5: Ground state and excited state probability Density

With the QHO Model for the same secular frequency different energy levels will evolve due to different n (principal quantum number) values. It can be visualized as –

Figure – 6: Different energy levels for different n values

This is the quantized motional energy of the ion **along one axis only** rather than the full 3D energy.

A real ion in a Paul trap oscillates in x , y and z direction, each direction behaves approximately like an independent harmonic oscillator.

So, the TOTAL motional energy is:

$$E_{\text{total}} = E_x + E_y + E_z$$

or:

$$E = \hbar\omega_x \left(n_x + \frac{1}{2}\right) + \hbar\omega_y \left(n_y + \frac{1}{2}\right) + \hbar\omega_z \left(n_z + \frac{1}{2}\right)$$

4 Discussion and Result

Due to computational limitations associated with the available hardware resources, the time-dependent particle tracing simulation could only be performed over a relatively short time interval. As a result, the secular oscillatory behaviour was most clearly seen along the x -axis, while the y -axis displayed only partial oscillatory characteristics and the z -axis motion could not be fully captured within the simulated time window.

Therefore, the quantum harmonic oscillator analysis presented in this work was primarily performed using the secular frequency extracted from the x -direction motion of the trapped ion.

Despite this limitation, the obtained results successfully demonstrate the connection between the classical secular motion of a trapped ion and the corresponding quantum harmonic oscillator model.

Future work may involve longer-duration simulations with higher computational resources to extract and analyse the complete three-dimensional motional spectrum of the trapped ion.

4 References

- [1] M. Guggemos, D. Heinrich, O. A. Herrera-Sancho, R. Blatt, and C. F. Roos, “Sympathetic cooling and detection of a hot trapped ion by a cold one,” *New Journal of Physics*, vol. 17, no. 10, p. 103001, 2015.
- [2] J. Heinonen, M. Erdmanis, and I. Tottonen, “Simulation of Microfabricated Linear Ion Trap,” Aalto University, Department of Micro- and Nanosciences, Finland. [Simulation of Microfabricated Linear Ion Trap](#)
- [3] GitHub repository containing COMSOL simulation files, MATLAB scripts, and exported ion trajectory datasets: <https://github.com/OMtheBest172/Linear-Paul-Trap>